

Codebook | Aikido Expert Interviews

Computer-assisted coding with NVivo 12 and 13 (Lumivero. (2020). NVivo (Version 13, 2020 R1) [Computer software]. www.lumivero.com)

The codebook is the list of codes. The codes are labels that define what the data we are analysing are about. Each code has a definition. It helps to apply a code in a consistent way and it enables to share the codes with other researchers.

The codebook has been created in four steps. Upon each step, professor Ellen Van Praet conducted some pilot coding to give feedback. The first version was too extensive. It contained too many codes from existing frameworks. This was the result of advice certain non-involved researchers had given as soon as they heard about the research. The second version focused on the research question at hand only. It proved, however, to contain an unnecessary hierarchy. This hierarchy had hardly any added value for the coding process and constituted, in fact, an analysis of the data in itself. By creating a shallow hierarchy of two levels, the coding process is more open to new or different interpretation and analysis. The third version had a simple parent and child hierarchy. The fourth and current version showed some clearer code names and no longer had absence or non-occurrence codes. Any absence relevant for the research could become apparent in the NVivo analysis and visualisation features. Codes may still be drawn from both the planned manual and computer-assisted methods.

Parent Codes

1. **Aikido Principles** – to benchmark the principles
2. **Aikido Pedagogy** – to prepare further steps in this research project
3. **Applied Aikido** – to illustrate possible applications
4. **Aikido Challenge** – to challenge the pros and cons of aikido as a source domain
5. **Aikido Techniques** – to refer to in an embodied pedagogy
6. **Memorable quotes**

Parent Codes and Child Codes

See table on the following pages.

Name	Description
1. Aikido Principles	The aikido principles refer to aspects of aikido in a broad sense, such as core ideas, goals, techniques, pillars, philosophy and symbolism. These aikido principles are under investigation to answer the first research question: to what extent do the principles of aikido serve intercultural understanding and communication?
Adaptability	Adaptability to different situations, developments and behaviours.
Anthropocosmism	The anthropocosmic worldview which envisions humanity as one body with Heaven, Earth and Myriad Things, rather than the anthropocentric worldview which envisions humanity as the center of the whole universe. (Jia & Jia, 2016)
Assertiveness	Taking action towards the other person (atemi). Dorland's Medical Dictionary defines assertiveness as: a form of behavior characterized by a confident declaration or affirmation of a statement without need of proof; this affirms the person's rights or point of view without either aggressively threatening the rights of another (assuming a position of dominance) or submissively permitting another to ignore or deny one's rights or point of view.
Clarity	Creating clarity by carefully taking steps towards a desired outcome.
Closeness	Closeness is a partnering attitude of blending with the other person, with softness and a willingness to build common ground. Aikido emphasizes working with a partner, rather than grappling or fighting against an opponent as in competitive tournaments. The essence of the practice is the blending of movements and breathing (waza) which physically creates harmony in conflictual encounters (Faggianelli & Lukoff, 2006). It is often referred to as blending, unification, awase and musubi.
Cooperation	Cooperation is a harmony attitude of taking the perspective of the other and building common ground. Cooperation is an intention-oriented practice (Kecskés, 2020). It is the intention to cooperate with the other(s).
Economy	Minimisation of effort or impact
Embodiment	Embodiment is the incorporation of what one has learned by combining the cognitive and the physical experience.
Empathy	Empathy is the ability to initiate communication with other individuals respectfully, observe and react with verbal and nonverbal sensitivity. (Tong-Toomy nog te downloaden) in (Nadeem et al., 2018) Empathy was defined as the ability to participate in cognitive and emotional role-taking behaviour (Spitzberg & Cupach, 1984) nog te downloaden, in (Arasaratnam, 2006)
Flexibility	Flexibility to select from techniques, skills, knowledge, understanding and attitudes.

Inward growth	Inward growth refers to the fundamental human values (e.g. work ethic and respect) some expect to learn through martial arts training: self-actualisation, self-esteem, value development, achievement and cultural awareness. Some testimonials: Martial arts has helped me understand the value of hard work. Martial arts teaches me lessons that I may not learn elsewhere. Martial arts has helped me to be more respectful to others. (Ko & Kim, 2010)
Noble outcome	Attitude and skills to achieve an outcome in which all people involved feel adequately satisfied. Intercultural communication is seen as a means to overcome difference – be it cooperatively (“good intercultural communication leads to greater understanding”) [win-win] or competitively (“good intercultural communication helps to beat the other at their own tricks”) [win-lose]. (Piller, 2017) One day, he realized that ‘Aikido exists beyond all those techniques and apart from the settlement of victory
Openness	Openness to observe and invite with positivity, curiosity, flexibility on the one hand and with a focus on the moment, not on prior assumptions or thoughts, on the other hand. General openness to intercultural learning and to people from other cultures, withholding judgment (Deardorff, 2006). The positive attitude sensation-seekers have toward people from other cultures is fostered by the fact that such people represent a form of novelty – hence high sensation seekers’ motivation to interact with them (Ara
Other-awareness	Other-awareness is fostered by studying, understanding and learning about others and their values.
Other-relative view	The other-relative view here seeks to see the other in relation to one self, the possible inequality included. It is similar to tenkan, sometimes kaiten, in aikido.
Outward development	The outward development focuses on interpersonal interaction, confrontation, self-defence and combat. Self-defence is an application of the defensive skills developed through sparring and form drills to life-threatening situations. Some testimonials: martial arts helps me develop self-defence ability. Martial arts helps me to be aware of my ability in self-defence situations. Martial arts makes me feel confident that I can protect others and myself in dangerous situations. (Ko & Kim, 2010)
Purity	Perfection of aikido in all its principles and in communication with others and the situation.
Respect	Respect to value others without judgment, valuing other cultures, cultural diversity (Deardorff, 2006).
Safety	Safety refers to safe behaviour, i.e. behaving effectively and efficiently without doing harm to other and self.
Self-awareness	Self-awareness is fostered by studying, understanding and learning about oneself and one’s values.
Situation-awareness	
Softness	Softness in the ‘hardness’ of an attack or any aikido interaction is key: if someone grabs your wrist, what you really want to do is increase the contact on your wrist and at the same time soften yourself so that there is a fuller contact between you and the attacker, and then subtly turn and arrange your body in such a way that you’re able to be present, soft, relaxed, and connected with them. (Faggianelli & Lukoff, 2006)

Spirituality	The quality of being connected with religion or the human spirit. (Online Oxford Learner's Dictionary) Spirituality means different things to different people, what is mentioned as "spiritual" for one may not be spiritual for another. (Detert et al., 2006)
Stepping in	
Stepping out	
Tranquillity	Tranquillity to remain calm, centred, grounded, alert and in the moment. (On Martial Aesthetics with Dr Wayne Wong (Hong Kong Polytechnic University, 2020) It is both a physiological and a mental state. The mental calmness is often referred to as an empty mind, a beginner's mind (mushin).
Universal harmony	Conviction that one's harmony attitude is linked to a universal harmony of humankind. 'Reform your perception of how the universe actually looks and acts; change the martial techniques into a vehicle of purity, goodness, and beauty; and master these things. When the sword of harmonization linking heaven, earth, and humankind is manifest, one is liberated, able to purify and forge the self.' (Ueshiba, 2013)
Upward growth	The upward growth is the development and transformation in a person towards all humanity or the universe, the cosmos, or any higher realm. [Self-derived from growth, self-growth and the visual position in the adapted Deardorff pyramid model.]
2. Aikido Pedagogy	Aikido pedagogy refers to the way aikido teachers approach teaching aikido. It also refers to how they see the learning process. For this research: aikido pedagogy is investigated as a source of intercultural teaching and learning and to prepare the second and third research questions: (1) How efficient is the use of aikido in teaching intercultural communication skills? (2) How effective is aikido-based intercultural training in intercultural and multilingual encounters?
Aikido community	
Deductive	Deductive approaches to teaching primarily explain and show the main success factors of an aikido movement. The students then try out the movement and learn by seeing, listening and translating the explanation into movement.
Etiquette	
Explicit	In an explicit teaching approach, the teacher talks about the principles and meaning of aikido and not just the self-defence or combat aspects. The meaning of aikido can range from the harmony attitude to the self-development and even spirituality.
Implicit	In an implicit teaching approach, the teacher does not talk about the principles or meaning of aikido and limits teaching to talking about the self-defence or combat aspects.
Inductive	Inductive approaches to teaching primarily show an aikido movement without any explanation. The students then try out the movement and learn by seeing, mimicking, feeling and discovering.
Intensity	

Path	
Circular path	A circular path is a learning path in which the learner passes by the learning steps many times in order to master the higher levels. It also refers to a learning process in which aspects of advanced-level learning are prominent before the more profound study of the basic level.
Linear path	A linear path is a learning path in which you learn step by step from what is considered to be the basic level towards more advanced and proficient levels of knowledge, skills and practice.
Society	The role an aikido dojo or school plays in the society.
3. Applied Aikido	Aikido as a source domain applied in a target domain of e.g. psychotherapy, physiotherapy, conflict management or communication.
Conscious application	When one applied aikido outside the dojo as a strategy in an interaction or in life and was purposefully inspired by aikido, they applied it consciously.
Metaphorical application	Aikido as a metaphor, model or strategy to deal with a situation or an interaction.
Physical application	Aikido as a physical application to defend oneself in an altercation or any physical interaction.
Subconscious application	When one applied aikido outside the dojo as a strategy in an interaction or in life and only realised in hindsight that it was indeed inspired by aikido, they applied it subconsciously.
4. Aikido Challenge	Aikido's challenge refers to any pros and cons of aikido as a system. It refers to the aspects that make aikido unique or not. It also refers to possible inconsistencies or shortages.
Shortcoming	A shortcoming refers to a weakness, inconsistency, flaw or shortage in aikido.
Efficiency and effectiveness	
History	
Individual or situational shortcoming	
Political strategy	
The martial art of harmony	In the dichotomy of aikido being the way of a martial art and the way of harmony at the same time, harmony refers to a moral or ethical aspect of aikido (cf. some of the codes under 1. Aikido Principles).
Having the power to do harm gives the power to seek harmony	
Individual or situational martial art of harmony	
Uniqueness	The uniqueness of aikido is the belief that aikido is unique as a martial art or as a system. It may also refer to mere or certain aspects of aikido which are unique.
Budo rather than aikido	More general martial arts than specific for aikido.

Everything is unique	
5. Aikido Techniques	Aikido techniques to refer to in an embodied pedagogy. This is a descriptive category.
Atemi	An aikido atemi is a preemptive strike, usually delivered by nage to control uke or cause him to react. It is not the intention to harm the uke, it is the intention to stall them and to protect yourself at the same time. It keeps the attacker from continuing their attack.
Awase	To harmonize with the other.
Finger-hara control	
Gyakuhanmi katatedori	In the cross position, one hand holds the nage's other side wrist.(right hand-left wrist) (https://www.odtuaikido.org/en/techniques/)
Hara	Lower abdomen, center of body mass, source of physical power and breath. More formally called seika-tanden. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Henka waza	Changing from one technique to another
Ikkyo	"First teaching." The first technique in the osaewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Irimi	The aikido principle of entering inside of and moving through an attack. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Iriminage	A throw executed from irimi. Part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Jiyuwaza	A practice where nage responds freely, with any technique and without prior agreement, to uke's attacks. In jiyūwaza, the attack is usually prescribed (for example, shōmen-uchi or yokomen-uchi), as opposed to randori, where attacks are random. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Jujinage	Jūji means the character for ten, written as a cross. In jūjinage, uke's arms are crossed, like the character for ten. Part of the basic nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Kaeshi waza	Counter techniques
Kaitennage	Kaiten means to turn or spin. A throwing technique that is part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Katadori	Shoulder grab or hold. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Katatedori	One hand grab or hold. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Ki	Life energy, qi or chi in Chinese.
Kiai	A martial shout (used to effect an opponent's mind and to gain an advantage). Also, to be animated and energetic (literally, "to meet with ki"). Note: Kiai is generic; there are different kinds of kiai and different

	applications depending upon the circumstances and desired effect. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Kihon(waza)	"Foundational techniques." The basic technical curriculum of aikido. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Kikentaiichi	Spirit, weapon/technique and body are one unity.
Kokyu	Breathing, breath, breathwork, breath strength: the combination of concentration, ki and breathing with movement. https://aikido-amsterdam.com/what-is-aikido/commonly-used-terms Hara kokyu
Koshinage	"Hip throw." Koshinage is not one but a set of techniques where uke is thrown over nage's hip. Part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Kote gaeshi	"Turning of the forearm" throw. Part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Maai	The spacing and timing of an encounter. "Ma" means space or interval; "ai" means meeting. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Makoto	The quality of integrity, truthfulness, and sincerity of character. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Masagatsu agatsu katsuhayabi	"Truse victory is victory over self, victory in the moment." The phrase appears in the Kojiki, Japan's most ancient chronical of the age of the gods, as the name of a diety. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Metsuke	Gaze, expression of the eyes. During practice, the eyes should be alert and perceptive. Likewise, the readiness and alertness of an opponent can be gauged by the expression of his/her eyes. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Mikiri	Cutting look: sharpness of perception, assessment, evaluation, inside and out
Misogi	Rite of purification, as practiced in Shintō. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Mushin	Beginner's mind, empty mind, no mind
Musubi	Connection. The physical, mental, and spiritual connection between nage and uke. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Nage	"Thrower;" in partner practice, the role of the person executing the technique. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Nikyo	"Second teaching." The second technique in the osaewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)

Osaewaza	"Pinning technique." The generic term for any technique where uke is rendered immobile with a pin, as distinguished from nagewaza, where uke is thrown. Joint locks. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Oyowaza	"Applied technique(s)." The application (including modification) of technique to particular circumstances and a particular attack. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Randori	Multiple attackers. "Ran" means riotous or disorderly; "tori" means attack. In randori practice, uke may use any attack (as distinguished from jiyūwaza, where the attack is prescribed) and nage responds accordingly. Also, randori is usually practiced against multiple opponents. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Sankyo	"Third teaching." The third technique in the osaewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Sensitivity exercise	To learn how to sense the other and the surroundings.
Shihonage	"Four directions throw." Part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Shisei	Posture, verticality, stability
Shizentai	Natural stance, related to shi sei. Natural stance (as opposed to an assumed stance, such as hanmi).
Shomenuchi	Open-handed, vertical strike to the forehead. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Suki	An opening, a hesitation, a weakness in the opponents attack.
Sumikiri	Literal meaning: clear cut; other meaning: the clarity of the cut/move and the mind (of advanced practitioners).
Suwariwaza	"Seated technique." The generic term for waza executed from a seated position against an also seated attacker (as opposed to hanmi-handachi, where nage is seated but uke is standing). (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Taisabaki	Movement of the body: Taisabaki's are the basic movements in Aikido that you use to move to a safe position when you are attacked. Taisabaki's can be divided into incoming and outgoing movements (irimi and tenkan). Aikido is an art of self-defence in which there is no direct confrontation at the point of attack. That is why in Aikido we move out of the line of attack. https://aikido-amsterdam.com/what-is-aikido/commonly-used-terms
Tenkan	A pivot or turn. In aikido training, tenkan also refers to an entering turn against a one-hand wrist grab (see also tai-no-henkō). Also, tainohenko: The name given by the founder to a basic entering and turning exercise conducted against a one-hand wrist grab. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)

Tenshi	Heaven and earth, verticality
Tenshinage	"Heaven and earth throw." Part of the nagewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Todome	Fatal or finishing blow, coup de grâce
Ukemi	Rolling, falling and breakfall techniques
Unbendable arm	A posture, stability, and projection exercise
Yawara	The kanji for yawara and ju in jujutsu or judo is the same (柔). The kanji also translates to "flexibility" or "giving way". Another term for yawara is tenouchi which translates to "inside the hand". It is also a small rod, made of wood, that extends somewhat from both ends of a person's fist.
Yin-yang	
Yonkyo	"Fourth teaching." The fourth technique in the osaewaza curriculum. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
Zanshin	"Remaining mind or attention;" exercise of mental alertness or readiness, especially following the completion of a technique. (https://asu.org/student-handbook/glossary-of-aikido-terms/)
6. Memorable quotes	Quotes which might be referred to, or even worth clipping the audio.
Common ground	
Equality	Equality and inequality; the exchangeable roles of uke and tori/nage
Inconceivability	A (temporary or permanent) state of being impossible to conceive. Not being able to understand or to consider.
Intercultural encounters	
Litmus test	
Principles	
Recipient design	
Words	